

Fig. S1. Schemes on the experimental setup and sampling of the logs at each location. A) Log preparation from a *Q. serrata* stem killed by oak wilt disease. B) Location of the 40 logs at each site. C) A pile with 4 logs at Aobayama. D) Drill sampling from a log.

Fig. S2. Regression lines between the copy number of the five standard moc DNA and the sequence read numbers of the amplicons obtained after MiSeq sequencing of each sample. Top: Aobayama, Middle: Yamashiro, Bottom: Tano. Left: 2016_Autumn, 2017_Spring, and 2017_Summer. Right: 2017_Autumn and 2018_Spring. The standard DNA concentrations were set to be higher in the right figures than in the left figures because the former samples may contain a larger amount of fungal DNA as the decomposition of wood progressed.

Fig. S3. Changes in taxonomic composition of fungal OTUs detected from *Q. serrata* logs in the three forest sites. Left, DNA copy number; Right, Percentage of DNA copy number (relative abundance); Top, Healthy logs; Bottom, Wilt logs.

Fig. S4. Two-dimensional NMDS ordination plots showing dissimilarities in the fungal community composition detected from *Q. serrata* logs in each study site at each sampling time based on the Bray-Curtis index. The data from 41 outlier samples, plotted extremely distant from other plots, were removed from the analysis. Vectors indicate the direction and magnitude of numeric factors significantly associated with the variation of fungal communities. Asterisks on the top right of each figure show the significant difference in the fungal community between wilt and healthy logs: ***, $P < 0.001$; **, $P < 0.01$; ns, not significant. For detailed stats, please refer to Table S6 .

Fig. S5 Comparison of diversity indices of fungal communities in *Q. serrata* logs between healthy logs and wilt logs in Aobayama (bars represent standard errors of the mean; t-test ***, $P < 0.001$) (A) along sampling days (B), with the result of ANCOVA (C) where sampling days were set as covariant.

C

Factor	Shannon Index			Simpson Index			Pielou's Evenness		
	Sum sq	F	P	Sum sq	F	P	Sum sq	F	P
wilt	4.01	8.31	0.0042	0.81	12.03	<0.001	2.10	27.87	<0.001
days	19.06	39.51	<0.001	2.18	32.44	<0.001	1.32	17.55	<0.001
wilt*days	0.74	1.53	0.22	0.03	0.47	0.50	0.81	10.78	0.0011

Fig. S6 Comparison of diversity indices of fungal communities in *Q. serrata* logs between healthy logs and wilt logs in Yamashiro (bars represent standard errors of the mean; t-test ***, $P < 0.001$) (A) along sampling days (B), with the result of ANCOVA (C) where sampling days were set as covariant.

Fig. S7 Comparison of diversity indices of fungal communities in *Q. serrata* logs between healthy logs and wilt logs in Tano (bars represent standard errors of the mean; t-test ***, $P < 0.001$) (A) along sampling days (B), with the result of ANCOVA (C) where sampling days were set as covariant.

Fig. S8 Wood density loss rate and wood moisture of *Q. serrata* logs at each sampling period in the three study sites. Results of the comparison between the top and bottom of the logs (Wilcoxon rank sum test) were shown at the top left of each figure: ns, not significantly different ($P > 0.05$); **, $P < 0.01$.